

Planar four-coordinate nickel(II) complexes of tridentate ligands incorporating azo-oxime-carboxyl chelation : synthesis and structure

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The tridentate azo-oxime-carboxylate ligands $\text{HON}=\text{C}(\text{Ar})\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CO}_2\text{H}$, H_2ArL (H_2PhL , $\text{Ar} = \text{Ph}$; H_2Tol , $\text{Ar} = p\text{-tolyl}$) have been used to synthesize dimeric and monomeric nickel(II) complexes of type $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{ArL})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$. The X-ray structure of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$ authenticates the planar four-coordinate NiN_3O geometry. The amino group of each molecule is hydrogen-bonded ($\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}$) to the uncoordinated carboxylate oxygen of the adjacent molecule resulting in an infinite supramolecular chains with hydrogen bonded $\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}$ distance 2.949(5) Å.

The oxime function ligated as in motif 1 played a vital role for redox activation of pseudo-octahedral nickel especially over the valance states 2–4^{1–3}. The function is generally employed in conjugation with other donors ensuring chelate formation. Notable examples of bidentate chelators of this type, 2, are dioximes ($\text{X} = \text{NOH}$)^{1a,4}, imine oximes ($\text{X} = \text{N}$)^{2b} and ketoximes ($\text{X} = \text{O}$)⁵. In this context bidentate azo oxime^{3a}, 3 has also received much attention.

Recently we explored the feasibility of attaching carboxyl function to azo-oxime functions by synthesising a family of acyclic tridentate N, N, O ligands, 4, (abbreviated as H_2ArL)^{6–8}. The ligand is crucial for redox-activation and spin-pairing of pseudo-octahedral transition metal complexes^{6–8} especially in the cases of manganese⁶, iron⁷, and cobalt⁸. It also afforded monomeric square planar palladium(II) and platinum(II) carboxylates^{9,10} of biological interest. The above findings prompted us to scrutinise the behaviour of nickel towards the ligand. Initially dimeric (1 : 1) nickel complexes of type $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})_2]$, 5, is formed, which on treatment with $n\text{-BuNH}_2$ afforded

reddish brown adduct of type $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$, 6 (Scheme 1). Structure and spectral behaviour of the complexes are scrutinised. The X-ray structure of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$ authenticates the tridentate mode of coordination.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The two ligands used are H₂PhL and H₂ToL. The stoichiometric (1 : 1) reaction of H₂ArL, **4**, with Ni^{II}(MeCO₂)₂·4H₂O in methanol afforded dark brown diamagnetic (spin-paired, *d*⁸) solids. The complexes are insoluble in methanol, dichloromethane and acetonitrile but soluble in dimethylformamide probably due to the formation of a dimeric species of composition [Ni₂^{II}(ArL)₂], **5**. The analytical (C, H, N) data and one ν_{NO} stretch around 1280 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum may confirm the dimeric formulation of [Ni(ArL)]. Unlike manganese, iron and cobalt complexes⁶⁻⁸, nickel failed to afford bis chelates of type [Ni^{II}(ArL)₂] or [Ni^{III}(ArL)₂]⁻. Treatment of [Ni₂^{II}(ArL)₂] with *n*-BuNH₂ in dichloromethane leads to dissolution and from the solution, reddish-brown adduct [Ni^{II}(ArL)(*n*-BuNH₂)], **6**, has been isolated. They are neutral and soluble in dichloromethane, acetonitrile and dimethyl formamide. The complexes are diamagnetic (spin-paired, *d*⁸) and show two N–H stretches (symmetric and antisymmetric) in the region 3300–3500 cm⁻¹. They display multiple bands in the 825–480 nm region (Table 1).

Table 1. Spectral data of the nickel(II) complexes

Compd.	UV/Vis data	IR data
	λ _{max} , nm (ε, M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	ν _{NH₂} , cm ⁻¹
[Ni ₂ (PhL) ₂] ^a	820 (1740), 490 (8360)	3350, 3440
[Ni ₂ (ToL) ₂] ^a	825 (1600), 500 (9970)	3340, 3420
[Ni(PhL)(<i>n</i> -BuNH ₂)] ^b	790 (1240), 490 (6340)	3340, 3430
[Ni(ToL)(<i>n</i> -BuNH ₂)] ^b	795 (1190), 480 (6550)	3340, 3440

^aIn dimethylformamide solution. ^bIn dichloromethane solution.

The [Ni₂^{II}(ArL)₂] complexes did not afford good quality single crystals. The X-ray structure of [Ni^{II}(PhL)(*n*-BuNH₂)] has been determined. Discrete molecules constitutes the monoclinic lattice (*P*₂₁/*n*, *Z* = 4). Significant crystal data are collected in Table 2.

Complete atomic coordinates along with equivalent isotropic displacement parameters are given in Table 3. Selected bond parameters are listed in Table 4. A view of the complex is shown in Fig. 1. The packing diagrams along *a*-axis and *b*-axis are shown in Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b) respectively.

The nickel atom is four-coordinate, the NiN₃O coordination sphere being satisfactorily planar with a mean deviation of 0.05 Å. The five-membered azo-oxime chelate ring (NiN₃C) is nearly exactly planar (mean devia-

Table 2. Crystallographic data for [Ni^{II}(PhL)(*n*-BuNH₂)]

Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ Ni
Formula weight, amu	399.09
Crystal size, mm	0.36 × 0.42 × 0.32
Crystal system,	Monoclinic
<i>a</i> , Å	13.707(6)
<i>b</i> , Å	6.880(2)
<i>c</i> , Å	19.023(11)
β, deg	94.60(4)
<i>V</i> , Å ³	1788.2(14)
Space group	<i>P</i> ₂ ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>Z</i>	4
ρ(cal), Mg m ⁻³	1.482
μ(Mo-Kα), mm ⁻¹	0.563
<i>F</i> (000)	832
Total no. of reflections	2816
No. of unique reflections (<i>R</i> _{int})	2651
<i>R</i> 1 ^a , <i>wR</i> 2 ^b [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	0.0503, 0.1191
<i>R</i> 1, <i>wR</i> 2 (all data)	0.0820, 0.1459
GOF ^c	1.054
No. of parameters	334
Maximum, minimum Δρ, eÅ ⁻³	0.554, -0.560

$$^aR = \Sigma | |F_o| - |F_c| | / \Sigma |F_o|$$

$$^b wR2 = [\Sigma \{w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2\} / \Sigma \{w(F_o^2)^2\}]^{1/2}$$

$$w^{-1} = \sigma^2(F_o^2) + (aP)^2 + bP,$$

where *P* = (*F*_o² + 2*F*_c²)/3 and *a* (0.0404, 0.0706 and 0.0949 respectively) and *b* (4.0443, 22.0380 and 0.0 respectively) are constants adjusted by the program. ^cGOF = [Σ{w(*F*_o² - *F*_c²)²}/(*n* - *p*)]^{1/2}, where *n* is the number of data and *p* the number of parameters.

Table 3. Atomic coordinates [*×* 10⁴] and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters

[Å² × 10³] for [Ni^{II}(PhL)(*n*-BuNH₂)]. *U*_(eq) is defined as one third of the trace of orthogonalized *U*_{ij} factor

Atom	<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>U</i> _(eq)
Ni	6476(1)	-2269(1)	3754(1)	43(1)
O(3)	6661(2)	-2518(5)	2808(2)	53(1)
O(2)	6276(3)	-3379(6)	1711(2)	65(1)
O(1)	6951(2)	-2003(6)	5196(2)	69(1)
N(1)	5152(3)	-2586(5)	3670(2)	36(1)
N(2)	4729(3)	-2619(5)	4242(2)	41(1)
N(3)	6279(3)	-2218(6)	4704(2)	45(1)
N(4)	7852(3)	-1811(6)	3925(2)	53(1)
C(1)	6031(4)	-2935(7)	2293(3)	48(1)
C(2)	4950(3)	-2851(7)	2391(2)	43(1)
C(3)	4315(4)	-2955(8)	1778(3)	59(1)
C(4)	3323(4)	-2884(10)	1804(3)	80(2)
C(5)	2921(4)	-2679(10)	2443(3)	81(2)

Table-3 (contd.)

C(6)	3523(4)	-2597(8)	3055(3)	63(2)
C(7)	4524(3)	-2672(7)	3032(2)	43(1)
C(8)	5332(3)	-2446(6)	4838(2)	38(1)
C(9)	4907(3)	-2481(6)	5519(2)	40(1)
C(10)	3902(4)	-2656(7)	5527(3)	51(1)
C(11)	3455(4)	-2660(7)	6155(3)	60(2)
C(12)	4008(4)	-2494(7)	6787(3)	62(2)
C(13)	5000(5)	-2335(8)	6793(3)	65(2)
C(14)	5456(4)	-2326(7)	6166(3)	53(1)
C(15)	8497(4)	-3476(9)	3825(3)	73(2)
C(16)	9584(5)	-3081(11)	3849(4)	88(2)
C(17)	9992(6)	-2450(11)	506(4)	111(3)
C(18)	11172(6)	-2425(12)	4524(5)	133(3)

Table 4. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) and their estimated standard deviations for $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$

Distances			
Ni-N(1)	1.822(4)	N(2)-C(8)	1.353(6)
Ni-N(3)	1.849(4)	N(3)-C(8)	1.351(6)
Ni-O(3)	1.845(3)	O(1)-N(3)	1.268(5)
Ni-N(4)	1.914(4)	O(2)-C(1)	1.222(6)
N(1)-N(2)	1.273(5)	O(3)-C(1)	1.286(6)
N(1)-C(7)	1.432(5)		
Angles			
N(1)-Ni-N(3)	82.2(2)	N(4)-Ni-N(3)	92.9(4)
N(1)-Ni-O(3)	96.7(2)	N(3)-Ni-O(3)	175.7(2)
O(3)-Ni-N(4)	88.3(2)	N(1)-Ni-N(4)	174.5(2)

Fig. 1. Perspective view and atom labeling scheme for $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$, all atoms being represented by 30% probability ellipsoids.

tion, 0.005 Å) and the pendant phenyl ring is nearly coplanar (dihedral angle, 1.9°). The six-membered chelate ring (NiNC_3O) is approximately planar (mean deviation,

0.05 Å). The dihedral angle between the two chelate rings is 5.6°.

Of the three Ni-N bonds the one to the amine, Ni-N(4), is longer than the other two by 0.07 Å. The Ni-N(azo) bond is the shortest. The amino group of each molecule is hydrogen-bonded ($\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}$) to the uncoordinated carboxylate oxygen of the adjacent molecule. In this manner infinite supramolecular chains are formed and these constitute the lattice (Fig. 2). The hydrogen bonded ($\text{N-H}\cdots\text{O}$) is 2.949(5) Å.

Fig. 2(b). Packing diagram of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$, a view down *b*-axis.

Experimental

The electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer. A Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (CHN). The IR spectra were recorded in KBr disk

with the help of Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on a PAR 155 vibrating-sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific magnet. Solution electrical conductivities were measured with a Philips PR 9500 bridge, the solute concentration being 10^{-3} M.

Synthesis of ligands and complexes :

The ligands were synthesized as previously described⁷. The complexes were synthesised by a general method. Details for one representative case is given below. Solvents and reagents were used as obtained from commercial sources.

$[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})_2]$:

To a methanolic solution of H_2PhL (0.045 g, 0.20 mmol) was added a methanolic solution of nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (0.05 g, 0.20 mmol). The contents were allowed to stir for 4 h and the dark brown precipitate was filtered and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl_2 . Yield : 122 mg, 93% (Found : C, 51.51; H, 2.81; N, 12.79%. Reqd. for $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})_2]$, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6\text{Ni}_2$: C, 51.58; H, 2.76; N, 12.90%).

(Found : C, 53.23; H, 2.87; N, 12.31%. Reqd. for $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{ToL})_2]$, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6\text{Ni}_2$: C, 53.14; H, 2.95; N, 12.40%).

$[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$:

To a suspension of $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})_2]$ (0.10 g, 0.15 mmol) in dichloromethane was added a drop of *n*-BuNH₂ and the contents were allowed to stir for 1 h. The solution was then evaporated *in vacuo*, the solid was washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over fused CaCl_2 . Yield : 0.112 g, 92% (Found : C, 54.24; H, 4.96; N, 14.11%. Reqd. for $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Ni}$: C, 54.18; H, 5.02; N, 14.05%).

(Found : C, 55.14; H, 5.39; N, 13.47. Reqd. for $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{ToL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$, $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Ni}$: C, 55.25; H, 5.33; N, 13.57%).

X-Ray structure determination :

Crystals of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$ ($0.36 \times 0.42 \times 0.32$ mm) were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into dichloromethane solution followed by slow evaporation. The unit cell parameters were determined by the least-squares fit of 30 machine-centered reflections having 2 θ values in the range 15–30°. Data were collected at 293(2) K by the ω -scan technique in the range $1.77^\circ \leq \theta \leq 23.54^\circ$ on a Siemens R3m/V four-circle diffractometer with graphite-monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å). Two check reflections measured after every 98 reflec-

tions showed no significant intensity reduction. All data were corrected for Lorentz-Polarization effects. Out of 2816 reflections collected, there were 2651 unique reflections of which 1865 reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ were used for structure solution by direct methods. All the non-hydrogen atoms were made anisotropic (data-to-parameter = 4554/334). The structure was refined on F^2 by full-matrix least squares using all unique data. Hydrogen atoms were added at calculated positions (riding model). All calculations were done on a 166 MHz IBM compatible PC/AT using the Siemens SHELXTL-VER.5.03 program package¹¹. Significant crystal data are collected in Table 2. Atomic coordinates along with equivalent isotropic displacement parameters are given in Table 3. The hydrogen atom coordinates, complete bond lengths and angles, anisotropic thermal parameters, and the structure factor tables are submitted as Supplementary Materials.

Conclusion :

The main findings of this work will now be summarized. The acyclic tridentate azo-oxime-carboxylate ligand $\text{HON}=\text{C}(\text{Ar})\text{N}=\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CO}_2\text{H}$, H_2ArL , **1**, (Ar = Ph, *p*-tolyl) react with nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate, affording a brown diamagnetic compound of composition $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})_2]$ which is presumably dimeric due to oximate bridging. Upon treating with *n*-BuNH₂ in dichloromethane, $[\text{Ni}_2^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})_2]$ underwent facile displacement by *n*-BuNH₂ furnishing the reddish brown adduct $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{ArL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$. They are diamagnetic (spin-paired, d^8) and display multiple bands in the visible region. The X-ray structure of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{PhL})(n\text{-BuNH}_2)]$ has been determined revealing planar four-coordinate NiN_3O geometry. The amino group of each molecule is hydrogen-bonded (N—H---O) to the uncoordinated carboxylate oxygen of the adjacent molecule. In this manner infinite supramolecular chains are formed. The hydrogen bonded (N—H---O) distance is 2.949(5) Å.

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